

PWR In-Core Flow Field Reconstruction with Convolutional Neural Networks for Digital Twin Applications

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ABSTRACT

We present an open-source workflow that builds, simulates, and learns from a Westinghouse four-loop PWR flow domain to produce physically realizable, assembly-wise core-inlet mass-flow distributions for neutronics coupling. The CAD captures the fluid path from the four cold legs through the downcomer and lower plenum to the top-of-fuel plane, and the transient CFD employs a STRUCT- ϵ 2G-URANS closure with synthetic pump-induced swirl to reproduce heterogeneous inlet patterns (spanning ~ 60 – 115 kg/s per assembly) that progressively homogenize with height. To reduce CFD monitoring overhead while retaining fidelity, we train a compact 3D residual CNN with anisotropic dilations and copy-through masking on four axial planes to inpaint missing assembly flows; errors decrease monotonically with elevation and remain ~ 1 kg/s even in the most heterogeneous central region. Relative to state-of-the-art reactor CFD (RANS/LES/2G-URANS) and ML-based field reconstruction, our contribution is a reproducible end-to-end pipeline that presents a full four-loop PWR with pump-induced swirl, records time-resolved FA-wise flows, and demonstrates a fast inpainting surrogate to accelerate future high throughput studies. In the context of digital twins, the trained model serves as a data-assimilative, real-time surrogate for the inlet map—updating from sparse sensors, enabling rapid analyses, and reducing plane-monitor requirements while maintaining physically realizable distributions, thereby advancing high-throughput neutronics coupling and operational studies.

Keywords: Field Reconstruction, Computational Fluid Dynamics, Pressurized Water Reactor, Lower Plenum Mixing

1. INTRODUCTION

Pressurized water reactors (PWRs) are the most common power reactors in commercial operation, and full-scale computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations coupled with neutronics offer a route to more accurate core analyses. However, open access to detailed 3-D geometries and fluid-thermal models is rare. The BEAVRS benchmark provides dimensions of a four-loop Westinghouse PWR, listing the reactor vessel and core barrel diameters, fuel assembly and rod pitch, and baffle width[1]. These parameters underpin many proprietary CFD models but do not constitute enough information for an open CAD description. The only public blueprint that approaches a realistic plant design is OPEN100, an open-source project providing engineering schematics, construction schedules, and 3-D CAD models for a 100MWe PWR. The fact sheet emphasises that the design is open source, includes downloadable CAD files for most power-plant components, and aims to reduce barriers to entry for nuclear projects[2]. Nevertheless, OPEN100 is a small modular reactor with a single loop rather than the four-loop Westinghouse design present in many currently operating reactors. To our knowledge no public source provides

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a complete, high-fidelity four-loop PWR CAD/CFD model. This gap motivates the open-source model presented in our work.

Machine-learning (ML) techniques for field reconstruction are a complementary avenue for accelerating reactor analyses and enabling digital-twin updates from sparse measurements. Recent reduced-order decoders have demonstrated accurate state reconstruction from very sparse sensors, yielding fast surrogates suitable for online monitoring [3]. In nuclear settings, digital-twin studies increasingly treat sensor placement and field reconstruction jointly to optimize where to measure so that learned models can recover full field resolution [4]. These collectively indicate that data-efficient field reconstruction is maturing toward practical digital-twin operation.

These advances also clarify current gaps relevant to PWR applications. While there is growing literature on ML-based reconstruction for turbulent flows or small facilities, there remains a lack of openly available, full-scale four-loop PWR geometries and curated datasets designed expressly for benchmarking reconstruction of core flow maps from sparse monitors. Open geometry and CFD datasets are essential to establish comparable protocols (masks, noise models, sensor budgets) and to quantify how reconstruction quality scales with sensor sparsity and flow heterogeneity.

Our study addresses these needs by releasing an open four-loop PWR CAD/CFD model and using it to generate physically realizable core-inlet distributions. On top of these data, we train a 3D-CNN inpainting model to reconstruct “missing” assembly-wise mass flow from periodic plane-monitor masks and demonstrate accuracy across strongly heterogeneous inlet conditions. We further position this workflow within a digital-twin generative loop: (1) simulate to produce new distributions under varied operating states; (2) learn a fast field-reconstruction surrogate; (3) use predictive metrics to select the next most informative simulations or sensor placements; and (4) iterate as conditions or fidelity needs evolve. This loop operationalizes digital twin upkeep under sparse sensing and limited CFD budget, and it aligns with emerging best practices for data-driven twins that continually integrate simulation and inference.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. CAD Model Construction and Data Sources

We constructed a full four-loop PWR flow-domain CAD in SOLIDWORKS using publicly available references from BEAVRS geometric data for vessel/barrel/baffle/core envelope [1], an ORNL system-definition document for operating conditions and core internals dimensions [5], and the NRC Westinghouse Technology Systems Manual for selected plate and support features [6]. The modeled fluid domain extends from the four cold-leg nozzles, through the downcomer and lower plenum, up to the top-of-fuel plane to match the CFD inlet to the core (fuel-assembly) region.

The workflow included (1) extracting dimensions and topology from the sources; (2) building a parameterized sketch (vessel/barrel radii, baffle gap, core envelope); (3) generating revolved and extruded features (vessel, barrel, baffle, lower plenum) for the four-loop layout; (4) representing core support components and instrumentation/guide tubes with values extracted from design schematics; (5) defining fluid–solid interfaces and trimming to the flow domain. We use dimensions directly where references provided ranges or nominal values and extract other dimensions from images in the documents [1, 5, 6].

2.2. Turbulence Modeling

We adopt a scale-resolving unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) approach tailored for complex reactor hydraulics. Classical URANS keeps the unsteady term in the turbulence transport equations yet relies on an eddy-viscosity hypothesis and near-equilibrium between production and dissipation. In flows with jets, curvature, separation, and pump-induced swirl this often inflates ν_t and overly diffuses momentum and temperature fields [7]. To retain URANS robustness while selec-

Figure 1. Flow path and CAD visualization of 4-loop Westinghouse PWR

Table I. Key dimensions used to parameterize the SOLIDWORKS CAD model. Values are reported in both Imperial and SI units with primary sources.

Parameter	Imperial	SI	Source
System pressure	2250 psia	15.5 MPa	[1]
Inlet coolant temperature	557.6 °F	292 °C	[5]
Core barrel inner radius	74.0 in	187.96 cm	[1]
Core barrel outer radius	76.25 in	193.675 cm	[1]
Pressure vessel inner radius	86.5 in	219.71 cm	[1]
Pressure vessel outer radius	95.0 in	241.30 cm	[1]
Baffle width	0.875 in	2.2225 cm	[1]
Fuel assembly length	159.8 in	405.9 cm	[5]
Fuel assembly pitch	8.466 in	21.5 cm	[5]
Rod pitch	0.496 in	1.26 cm	[5]

tively resolving energetic structures, we employ a second-generation URANS (2G-URANS) framework [8] built on an anisotropic k - ε baseline with variable C_μ and nonlinear stress-strain extensions. The modeled viscosity is

$$\nu_t = C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon},$$

and the transport of k and ε follows the standard two-equation form with gradient diffusion and production-destruction terms. STRUCT-type models introduce a structure indicator that compares a resolved timescale, $\tau_r \sim |Q|^{-1/2}$ (with $Q = -\frac{1}{2}\bar{A}_{ij}\bar{A}_{ji}$ and $\bar{A}_{ij} = \partial\bar{u}_i/\partial x_j$), to the modeled timescale, $\tau_m = k/\varepsilon$. The ratio $\alpha = \tau_r/\tau_m$ modulates the closure so that $\nu_t \rightarrow f_m(\alpha)\nu_t$, smoothly transitioning from URANS-like behavior to local, mesh-independent resolution wherever coherent structures dominate [8]. In the STRUCT- ε , the dissipation equation is augmented by an additional source $C_{\varepsilon 3} k |\Pi|$, where $|\Pi|$ measures the magnitude of a principal invariant of the resolved velocity-gradient tensor; this term suppresses modeled dissipation in highly strained/rotating regions and effectively “hands back” en-

ergy to the resolved field [7]. Prior nuclear hydraulics studies indicate that this strategy recovers finer shear layers and more realistic unsteady content at a URANS-like cost [7].

2.3. Inlet Boundary Condition

The four cold legs discharge downstream of centrifugal reactor coolant pumps, which are known to introduce secondary motion and azimuthal nonuniformities at the vessel nozzles; these perturbations can bias downcomer transport and the core inlet distribution [9]. To reproduce this physics without explicitly meshing the pump, we impose a synthetic swirling inflow on each cold leg. In a local polar frame,

$$\mathbf{u}(r, \theta) = u_{ax} \mathbf{e}_z + \alpha u_{ax} \mathbf{e}_\theta,$$

where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a dimensionless swirl-strength parameter (ratio of tangential to axial speed). The equivalent Cartesian form used in the solver field function is

$$[U_x, U_y, U_z] = \left[-\alpha u_{ax} \frac{y}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + \varepsilon}}, \alpha u_{ax} \frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + \varepsilon}}, u_{ax} \right],$$

with a small $\varepsilon > 0$ to avoid a singularity at $r=0$. This inflow model is implemented via a user field function in STAR-CCM+ [10]. The prescribed α is treated as a configurable parameter to allow future sensitivity studies of downcomer/corer inlet patterns to pump-induced swirl [9].

2.4. Transient Setup and Data Acquisition

Because redistribution dynamics during pump operation are inherently unsteady, we perform transient simulations rather than steady RANS [11, 12]. The run is advanced using an implicit second-order temporal scheme with fixed time step and 5 inner iterations per step for stability and cost control. To quantify FA-wise inflow, we deploy planar monitors coincident with the fluid entrance of each fuel assembly (193 per layer); these planes are replicated every 0.5 m axially to form nine layers (total 1737 planes). At every time step the solver reports area-averaged mass flow through each plane, enabling time histories and space-time maps of the core inlet distribution. The configuration is summarized in Table II; figures in the next subsection illustrate the nozzle swirl, downcomer development, and the evolution of the FA-wise inlet field.

Table II. Transient setup and data collection summary.

Item	Value	Notes
Temporal scheme	Implicit, second order	$\Delta t = 5 \times 10^{-4}$, 5 inner iter.
Physical time	15 s	[10,15]s recording period
Monitors per layer	193 planes	One per fuel assembly inlet
Axial layers	9 layers	Uniform spacing of 0.5 m
Total monitors	$9 \times 193 = 1737$	Recorded every Δt
Recorded quantity	FA mass flow	Per plane and time step
Turbulence closure	STRUCT- ε	As described above
Solver & Mesher	STAR-CCM+	Version 2502.0001 [10]
Mesh Cell Count	91,276,900	1.83cm base mesh size

2.5. Machine-learning Field Reconstruction

We reconstruct missing core-inlet mass flow rates on a 15×15 core lattice using four axially separated planes. Let $L=4$ denote axial levels and T the number of timesteps. Each timestep is treated as an inde-

pendent sample. A fixed geometry mask $\mathcal{M}_{\text{geom}} \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$ restricts learning to physically meaningful cells, and a periodic missing mask $\mathcal{M}_{\text{miss}} \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$ (checkerboard pattern with user-set fraction) emulates sparse monitoring. The observed mask is $\mathcal{M}_{\text{obs}} = \mathcal{M}_{\text{geom}} \wedge \neg \mathcal{M}_{\text{miss}}$.

Data from the first four axial levels are loaded and stacked along a depth axis to form (T, L, H, W) . We draw a random split (80/10/10) over T . To avoid leakage, per-level scalars (μ_ℓ, σ_ℓ) are fitted only on training values within \mathcal{M}_{obs} and then applied to all splits:

$$z_\ell = \frac{x_\ell - \mu_\ell}{\sigma_\ell}, \quad \ell = 1, \dots, L.$$

For each timestep we build a 3D sample with channels

$$\mathbf{x} = [z \odot \mathcal{M}_{\text{obs}}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{obs}}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{geom}}] \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times L \times H \times W},$$

and the target

$$\mathbf{y} = z \odot \mathcal{M}_{\text{geom}} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times L \times H \times W}.$$

Normalized (z, y, x) coordinate channels are concatenated to \mathbf{x} to provide positional context.

We use a fully convolutional 3D network with a shallow stem, a trunk of residual 3D blocks, and a $1 \times 1 \times 1$ head. The residual blocks employ *anisotropic dilation*: dilation is applied in the in-plane (y, x) directions to expand the receptive field over fuel-assembly neighbors, while keeping unit dilation along the level axis to preserve axial alignment across the L planes. The network predicts an unconstrained field $\hat{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times L \times H \times W}$ which is combined with the inputs via a copy-through rule that preserves known values and fills only missing voxels:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = (z \odot \mathcal{M}_{\text{obs}}) + \mathcal{M}_{\text{miss}} \odot \hat{\mathbf{z}}.$$

Learning minimizes a masked mean-squared error over the missing region, with AdamW and a plateau-based learning-rate scheduler. The best model is chosen by validation loss and then used for testing. Predictions are de-normalized per level using (μ_ℓ, σ_ℓ) to recover kg/s. On the test split we report, for each axial level, MAE, MAPE, and R^2 computed over missing voxels only. We also generate per-level 15×15 maps of MAE and signed mean error, and histograms of individual errors, presented as 2×2 figure panels to compare all levels.

3. RESULTS

The CFD solution exhibits a highly heterogeneous and dynamically evolving core-inlet distribution (Fig. 2). At the core inlet (first axial layer), the assembly-wise mass flow spans ~ 60 – 115 kg/s, with pronounced temporal fluctuations over the 5 s recording window despite constant inlet conditions. The spatial pattern is biased toward the core center and shows clear radial asymmetry consistent with the imposed pump-induced swirl at the four cold legs, yielding quadrant-dependent preferential paths. As the coolant rises through the fuel assemblies, lateral mixing rapidly damps these gradients and the distributions become progressively more uniform with height, as reflected in the reduced spread of assembly flows on the upper sensor planes. We observe a checkerboard-like pattern in the final axial layer, with assembly flows confined to ~ 76.2 – 77.6 kg/s. We intend to investigate and resolve the cause of this patterning and suspect it may come from placing the planes at the boundary between mesh cells. However, given that crossflow has largely homogenized the field at upper axial levels, this artifact does not affect our conclusions for the proposed field reconstruction methodology.

The 3D inpainting model accurately reconstructs missing assembly flows across all axial planes (Fig. 3). The architecture is a fully convolutional 3D residual network with a 96-channel trunk and six residual

Figure 2. Time-averaged mass flow rate across 9 axial layers through the 15x15 core lattice.

blocks that use anisotropic dilation in the transverse directions (dilations 1–2–3–3–2–1 in $y-x$) while keeping unit dilation through the level axis ($k_{\text{depth}}=3$). Normalized (z, y, x) coordinate channels are appended to the three physical inputs (observed values, observed mask, and geometry mask) to improve spatial awareness. The regression head predicts a dense field that is combined via a copy-through rule, exactly preserving known voxels and filling only the masked ones. Despite the strong inlet heterogeneity, errors decrease monotonically with height as cross-flow diffuses the field. The largest deviations occur near the core center where sharp local spikes in mass flow amplify inter-assembly gradients, and, even there, maxima are $\sim 1\text{kg/s}$, and error histograms indicate near-zero bias with tight dispersion (Fig. 4).

For digital-twin applications, these results show that a compact learned reconstructor can serve as a fast “state-completion” module that fills in unmeasured assembly flows from a sparse set of plane monitors, which is precisely the situation faced by digital twins that must infer full-field conditions from limited sensors. Similar field-reconstruction ideas have been demonstrated in the broader twin/CFD community, where deep models recover hidden flow or temperature structure from sparse or indirect signals to support online monitoring and control. Our inpainting network plays the same role for PWR inlet maps by learning from CFD to produce near-real-time estimates, enabling a closed-loop in which the twin propagates physics from CFD of the physical geometry, uses the reconstructor to estimate unmeasured states, and re-trains with reactor operation. Further, from a compute perspective, the trained model could save on costs associated with extracting assembly-wise values by reducing the number of plane monitors the application must integrate over at each timestep. In extracting mass flow rate from 1737 plane monitors per timestep for this simulation, we note a significant increase in the time required to finish the run. Using the CNN to save on this cost could enable faster exploration of longer transient periods while still acquiring assembly-wise parameters.

Figure 3. Field reconstruction workflow to train a CNN to predict missing/unobserved mass flow rate measurements. The 2x2 plot displays mean absolute percent error (MAPE) across 15x15 core lattice at 4 axial levels.

Figure 4. Error histogram demonstrating near-zero model bias for under/over-prediction of mass flow rate across 4 axial levels.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We present an open-source, four-loop PWR CAD/CFD model and a data-driven pipeline to reconstruct assembly-wise core-inlet mass flow rates from sparsely sampled planes. The geometry and boundary conditions emulate pump-induced asymmetries and yield strongly heterogeneous inlet patterns that progressively homogenize with height. On this challenging field, a compact 3DCNN with anisotropic dilations achieved accurate inpainting across four axial levels, with errors highest only near the core center where sharp local peaks occur and remaining well below 1% error. The approach therefore enables high-throughput studies of FA-wise properties by reducing the number of CFD plane monitors needed for downstream multiphysics coupling. Future work will expand the dataset to probe lower-frequency flow oscillations and their impact on temporal stability of the inlet map. Further, systematically increasing the fraction of missing fuel assembly data to quantify model robustness and degradation with access to less field information will help validate the approach. Field reconstruction serves as a practical bridge between sparse instrumentation and high-fidelity fields, thus enabling reactor twins that fuse models and measurements for continual calibration and learning.

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